

A Case Study on the Role of *Virechana Karma and Shamana Aushadh* in *Vipadika* w.s.r. Palmoplantar Psoriasis

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Abstract:

In *Ayurveda*, skin disorders are broadly categorized under the term '*Kushtha*.' Among these, *Vipadika* is classified as *Kshudra Kushtha*, characterized by *Sphutanam* (cracks) on the palms or soles accompanied by *Tivravedana* (severe pain) and *Daha* (Burning sensation). *Vipadika* closely resembles palmo-plantar psoriasis, a chronic skin condition primarily affecting the palms and soles. The causative factors of *Vipadika* align with those of *Kushtha*, including dietary imbalances such as *Viruddha Aahara*, excessive intake of *Drava*, *Snigdha*, and *Guru Aahara*, *Vega Dharana*, and indulgence in unethical actions. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Virechana Karma* and *Shamana Chikitsa* in managing *Vipadika*.

Material and Method: A 37-year-old male patient with complaints of excessive dryness, pain, and fissures in palms and plantar region for 2 years, diagnosed as *Vipadika* (palmo-plantar psoriasis), was treated with *Shodhana poorvaka shamana chikitsa*. *Virechana karma* with *Trivritta Avaleha* and *Shamana Chikitsa* with *Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha*, *Avipattikar Churna*, *Mahatikta Ghrita*, *Khadiraarista*, *Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu*, and *Nimba Taila* (local application), Marked improvement was found after the *shodhana poorvaka shamana chikitsa*. **Conclusion:** *Shodhana* therapy effectively addresses the root cause of *Vipadika*, aiding in disease prevention and long-term management. These findings underscore the importance of integrating detoxification and palliative care for chronic skin conditions.

The combination of *Ayurvedic* modalities gives significant results in *Lakshanas* (symptoms) like *Panipada sphutana* (fissures in palms and plantar region), *Tivravedana* (severe local pain), *Daha* (burning sensation), and *Kandu* (itching) in a span of about 2 months.

Keywords: Palmar-Plantar Psoriasis, *Ayurveda*, *Panchakarma*, *Kushta*, *Shodhana*, *Shamana*.

Article Received: 10-02-2026,

Published: 21-03-2026

Pages: 24-30

DOI:

Conflict of Interest: **The authors declare no conflicts of interest.**

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International Journal of Science and Consciousness (IJSC): A Bio-Psycho-Spiritual approach,
Published by the Research Foundation for Science & Consciousness, Uttarakhand, India

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Introduction

Healthy skin depicts a healthy life. Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory condition mainly affecting the skin and joints. Its prevalence in India is about 0.44-2.8 percent. Males are affected by psoriasis two times as common as females.^[1] Beyond the core aspects of the disease, psoriasis has a significant emotional and psychosocial impact on individuals,

affecting social interactions.^[2] There are seven different forms of psoriasis: Psoriatic arthritis, nail psoriasis, guttate psoriasis, pustular psoriasis, erythrodermic psoriasis, and plaque psoriasis are some examples of psoriasis.^[3]

Plaque psoriasis is the most prevalent type, accounting for about 80% of all psoriasis cases. It leads to inflamed, red skin covered with white and silvery scales, often appearing on areas like the elbows, scalp, lower back, and knees. These patches can cause burning or itching sensations. Palmoplantar psoriasis is a subset of plaque psoriasis, representing 3-4% of all plaque psoriasis cases, and primarily affects the palms of the hands and soles of the feet.

Palmo-plantar psoriasis is its localized form that can exist alone in the absence of other typical psoriatic lesions or may accompany psoriatic lesions elsewhere.^[4] Palmoplantar psoriasis is a variant of psoriasis that characteristically affects the skin of the palms and soles. It features hyperkeratotic, pustular, or mixed morphologies.^[5]

The presence of sharply defined, symmetrically distributed erythematous plaques with silvery scales, particularly affecting the thenar and hypothenar eminences, knuckles of the hands, and insteps of the feet, along with regular and coarse nail pitting in the absence of nail-fold lesions, is indicative of psoriasis. In contrast, ill-defined, usually asymmetrically distributed plaques are more characteristic of other dermatological conditions. The exact cause of palmoplantar pustulosis is unknown. However, palmoplantar psoriasis is caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors. The most common genetic factor associated with palmoplantar psoriasis is the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) Cw6.^[6]

Psoriasis affecting the palms and soles shares striking similarities with *Vipadika*, a condition described in *Ayurveda*. As one of the varieties of *Kushudrakushtha* (dermatological disorders), *Vipadika* is characterized by the involvement of *Vata-Kapha Dosh*. *Acharya Charaka* vividly describes it as causing *Tioravedana* (intense pain) and *Pani-Padasphutan* (painful cracks in the palms and soles), emphasizing the severity and impact of this condition.

The irritation of *Doshas* due to *Kushta Nidanas* triggers *Agnimandya* (digestive imbalance) and *Dhatu Shaitilyata* (weakening of muscles and other tissues). Among the *Doshas*, *Vata* and *Kapha* are most affected, leading to obstruction in the *Lomakupa* (sweat glands), *Twaka* (skin), *Rakta* (blood), *Mamsa* (muscles), and *Lasika* (channels). This disturbance vitiates the *Sweda Vaha Srotas* (sweat channels). The vitiated *Doshas* penetrate the *Rasa-Raktadi Dhatus*, particularly affecting the *Sanchara* (movement) in the *Tiryaka Siras* (veins) and eventually settling in the *Twaka*, manifesting as *Kushta*.^[7]

Case Report

A 37-year-old male patient was complaining of excessive dryness, burning sensation, sometimes itching, pain, and fissures in both palms and plantar region for 2 years. He took allopathic treatment for the same but did not get complete relief. He has no significant family history of autoimmune disorders or past medical or psychological history.

History of Past Illness

Patient did not have any known history of congenital anomalies and attained all developmental milestones without any delay. No history of surgery. No history of major illness such as hypertension, bronchial asthma, thyroid disease or diabetes.

History of Present Illness

Patient complained of hyperkeratosis with erythema, scaling, and fissures in the palm (some portion of the thenar, hypothenar, and central portion) of both the hands and plantar region for last 2 years. Patient took allopathic medication, but there was no satisfactory relief, so he came to the OPD of Rishikul campus, Haridwar, for further management through Ayurveda.

Personal History

- Appetite: Mild
- Bowel: mostly constipated, passes stool, once in two days
- Micturition: Regular
- Sleep: Sound
- Food: Mixed diet

General Examination

- Appearance: Normal
- Built: Moderate
- Nourishment: Moderate
- Pallor: Absent
- Icterus: Absent
- Oedema: Absent
- Cyanosis: Absent

Clinical Findings

On examination, the patient had blackish-red discolouration on both palms and plantar region with scaly, ill- defined erythematous plaques with watery discharge. He had severe itching and burning sensation on the sites.

Differential Diagnosis

Palmo-plantar psoriasis, Tylosis (Palmoplantar-keratoderm), and Dermatitis are the diseases that have the same clinical presentation among the patients and can be confused during the treatment. While treating the diseases, it is important to find out the difference between these diseases, which is useful for further lines of treatment. In *Ayurveda* Differential diagnosis can be made between *Vipadika kushtha*, *sidhma kushtha* and *ek kushtha*.

Diagnosis

After proper *roga* and *rogi pariksha* in *Ayurveda*, *Vipadika kushtha* was diagnosed to the patient for further management.

Treatment

After proper evaluation of *ashtavidha* and *dashvidha ayurvedic pariksha* in the patient, following Treatment was given to the patient: *Shodhana chikitsa* followed by *Shamana* therapy. *Shodhana* includes *Virechana karma* with *Trioritta Avaleha* as well as *Shamana* therapy with *Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha*, *Avipattikar Churna*, *Khadiraarista*, *Panchatikta Ghruta Guggulu*, and *Nimba Taila* (local application), marked improvement was found after the *shodhana poorvaka shamana chikitsa* .

Treatment Plan

Table 01

Medicine	Dose	Route	Duration
Deepana Pachana with Chitrakadi Vati (250 mg)	2 tablets thrice a day	Oral	5 days
Snehapana with Panchatikta Ghrita	30ml -1 st day, 45ml- 2 nd day, 60ml - 3 rd day, 80ml- 4 th day 120ml- 5 th day	Oral	5 days
Sarvanga Abhyanga followed by Nadi Swedana	Nimbadi taila L/A followed by Bashpa Swedana	External application	3 days
Virechana Karma	Trivritta Avaleha 25 gm	Oral	At 10 a.m (once)

Patient was given *Trivritta Avaleha* (25gm) as virechana yoga at 10.00 am. Vitals were noted at regular intervals (pulse, B.P., Temperature, Respiration rate). The number of bouts of bowel evacuation (Vega) were 18 (*Madhyama vega* were achieved). *Samsarjana Krama's* specific diet schedule was followed by the patient for 5 days.

Shamana Aushadha

Table 02

Medicine	Dose	Route	Duration
Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha	40 ml BD Empty stomach twice daily	Oral	1 month
Avipattikar Churna	3gm BD with luke warm water	Oral	1 month
Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu	2 tablets BD (crushed) with luke warm water	Oral	1 month
Khadiraarista	20 ml BD with an equal amount of water after taking meal	Oral	1 month
Nimba Taila		External Application	1 month

The patient was tested on subjective criteria which includes *Vedana* (Pain), *Kandu* (Itching), and *Daha* (Burning sensation) [Table: 3], and on objective criteria, *Panisphutana* (cracks) is observed Table: -4.

Subjective Criteria

Table 03

Sr. No	Criteria	Grade	Symptoms
1	<i>Vedana</i> (Pain)	0	No Pain.
		1	Pain after pressing.
		2	Pain on touch.
		3	Pain without touching.
2	<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	0	No itching.
		1	Itching 1-2 times a day.
		2	Frequent itching.
		3	Itching disturbs sleep.
3	<i>Daha</i> (Burning sensation)	0	No Burning sensation.
		1	Burning during itching.
		2	Continuous burning.

Objective Criteria

Table 04

Sr. No	Criteria	Grade	Symptoms
1	<i>Pani-pada sphutana</i> (cracks)	0	No cracks.
		1	Cracks on palm or sole only.
		2	Cracks on palm and sole.
		3	Cracks on the Complete foot and complete hand.

Results and Discussion

Following Shodhana poorvaka shamana chikitsa of Ayurveda, patient showed remarkable improvement. There was a noticeable reduction in scaling and discoloration, itching and pain had completely resolved. The texture of the palm returned to normal, allowing the patient to carry out daily activities without discomfort. The patient experienced complete relief from the symptoms of *Vipadika* (palmo-plantar psoriasis), highlighting the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic* management in such cases.

Table 05

Parameters	BT	AT
<i>Vedana</i> (Pain)	2	0
<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	3	0
<i>Daha</i> (Burning sensation)	2	0
<i>Padshutana</i> (cracks)	3	1

BT

AT

The *Panchakarma* treatment demonstrated its unique efficacy in eliminating accumulated toxins (*Ama*) and restoring the balance of bioenergies (*Doshas*) at both physical and mental levels. In this case, *Virechana* (therapeutic purgation) yielded promising results when combined with *Shamana Yoga* (palliative herbal formulations). This integrative approach contributed significantly to the overall improvement in the patient's condition.

Virechana is one of the *Shodhana Chikitsa* specially advised in the *Pitta* and *Rakta Pradhana* disorders and is very effective in various skin diseases. In all skin disorders, there is an accumulation of *Kledana*. *Virechana* has *Pitta Shodhana* and *Rakta Prasadhana* property leads to *Kledana Hara*.^[8]

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Avipattikar Churna- *Avipattikar Churna* is a classical *Ayurvedic* formulation traditionally indicated for *Pitta* pacification, digestive disturbances, and mild purgation. In the context of palmar psoriasis (*Vipadika*), it plays a supportive role by addressing underlying *Pitta-Kapha* vitiation and *Ama* accumulation, which are considered important pathogenic factors in skin disorders. By improving *Agni* (digestive fire), reducing hyperacidity, and facilitating the elimination of toxins, *Avipattikar Churna* helps in reducing systemic inflammation associated with psoriasis.^[9] Its mild purgative action is comparable to *Mridu Virechana*, a therapy often employed in *Kushtha* management, and is believed to expel aggravated *Pitta* and metabolic waste.^[10]

Mahamanjsthadi Kwatha- *Mahamanjsthadi Kwatha* is a classical *Ayurvedic* decoction centered on *Manjistha* (*Rubia cordifolia*) and is widely used as a blood-purifying and skin-supportive remedy; when applied in palmar (palmoplantar) psoriasis (*Vipadika*), it likely helps through both systemic and local actions. Pharmacologically, *R. cordifolia* contains anthraquinones and other phenolics with demonstrated antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and wound-healing activities, which can reduce oxidative stress, modulate inflammatory mediators, and help control secondary infection in psoriatic fissures and plaques.^[11]

Khadirarishta- Clinically, case reports document that *Khadirarishta*, when administered internally along with local therapies and *Virechana*, led to marked reduction in itching, fissures, dryness, and scaling in palmoplantar psoriasis patients.^[12]

Mahatikta ghrita: *Mahatikta ghrita* has a large number of herbs that are bitter in taste. *Tikta Rasa* helps in balancing *Pitta Dosha*. On the other hand, *Ghrita* itself mitigates *Pitta Dosha*. It acts mainly on *Kleda*, *Meda*, *Lasika*, *Rakta*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*, which helps in balancing the vitiated *Dosha* and *Dhatu*. It acts as *Raktasodhaka*, *Kushtaghna*, *Kandughna*, and *Varnya*.^[13]

Conclusion

This case study demonstrates the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* therapies in managing complex dermatological conditions such as *Vipadika* (palmoplantar psoriasis). The treatment protocol included *Deepana-Pachana* (enhancement of digestive fire and metabolic functions), *Shodhana* through *Virechana* (therapeutic purgation), and *Shamana Aushadhis* (palliative medicines). These interventions collectively supported *Amapachana* (digestion of metabolic toxins), elimination of vitiated *Doshas*, and establishment of *Samyavastha* (homeostasis or balance of *Doshas*). By addressing the root cause through *Virechana* and reinforcing the outcome with proper *Pathya Ahara* and *Vihara* (wholesome diet and lifestyle), the patient experienced notable symptomatic relief and sustained clinical improvement. This holistic approach disrupted the *Samprapti* (pathogenesis), alleviated the primary symptoms, and enhanced *Vyadhi-Kshamatva* (immunity/resistance). Hence, the treatment was found effective in relieving symptoms and preventing recurrence (*Anubandha*).

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